

The logo for MouldTech Systems features a solid orange square on the left. To its right, the word "MouldTech" is written in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with the "M" partially overlapping the orange square. Below "MouldTech", the word "Systems" is written in a smaller, black, sans-serif font. The background is light gray with abstract geometric shapes, including a large white arrow pointing right and several gray hexagons.

MouldTech
Systems

Drone spraying in agriculture, utilising controlled droplet application

Dissemination of the project „Development of spraying technologies for reduced environmental impact in agricultural applications”

GINOP-2.1.2-8-1-4-16-2018-00694

The role of meteorology in agriculture

Wind, and temperature

Wind speed is a primary influencer in droplet drift, temperature effects swath

Precipitation

It's usually a bad idea to spray in the rain...

The CDA technology

Hydraulic sprayer

Hydraulic systems use pressure to create a fluid film after the nozzle, which tears up do different sized droplets

CDA sprayer

A CDA sprayer uses a rotary disk to create thin fluid streams, which break up in evenly sized droplets

Our Technology

5

Improvements:

Improved internal flow

Pressure equalization

Results:

World class efficiency

Reliable, lightweight sprayer systems

Meteorology integration

Our system integrates datastreams from the MyDroneMet forecast system, enabling users more efficient operations.

Accurate forecasts

Our system gets relevant data through the MyDroneMet API, allowing better planning

Availability estimation

Using the MyDroneMet system, the operators can estimate system availability, and improve logistics

Weather warnings

The system provides weather warnings allowing a safer flight, and spraying

Efficiency prognosis

Using gathered spraying efficiency data, we can calculate the effects of different weather conditions on spraying

THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION

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